

POTENTIAL APPLICATION OF THE EUROPEAN SUSHEAT PROJECT CONCEPT TO THE COVERAGE OF INDUSTRIAL HEAT DEMAND

José Daniel Marcos¹, Rubén Barbero¹, Antonio Rovira¹, Iman Golpour¹, Richard Law², Silvia Trevisan³, Rafael Guedez³

¹ Department of Energy Engineering, National Distance Education University, UNED, Madrid, Spain

²UNEW School of Engineering, Newcastle University, Newcastle, UK

³Department of Energy Technology, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden

*Corresponding Author: jdmarcos@ind.uned.es

ABSTRACT

This study is a part of the European project "Smart integration of waste and renewable energy for sustainable heat upgrade in the industry (SUSHEAT)" which aims to effectively contribute to the decarbonization of heat demand used in the European industry. To this end, this project proposes an innovative approach that enables a cost-effective, flexible, user-oriented, and reliable heat upgrading concept with a smart integration of all available resources, aiming to achieve a heat supply temperature between 150 and 250 °C. Starting in May 2023, the project will face the main technological challenges to address the development of the key components of a new generation of high-efficiency industrial heat upgrading systems powered by renewable energy sources and waste heat recovery. It develops and validates three novel enabling technologies: High Temperature-Heat Pump, PCM bio-inspired TES system, and Control and Integration Twin (CIT) system. This work analyses the thermal demand profiles of diverse industry sectors, elucidating their distinctive heating requirements, design specifications, and operational boundaries, including factors such as hours of operation and working temperatures. While the primary focus revolves around specific use cases, notably the Mandrekas and Pelagia industries (located in Greece and Norway, respectively), our objective goes beyond these cases and 4 additional industries will be added for study as case studies. The knowledge gained will be instrumental in developing various industrial application scenarios, advancing the innovative SUSHEAT concept. This concept will be experimentally evaluated at KTH's laboratories in Stockholm (Sweden). Simultaneously, the research explores the potential applicability of the SUSHEAT concept at other end-user sites, augmenting the scope beyond the demonstration rig setup. In tandem with analyzing industrial heat demand, we investigate the availability of various energy resources, including waste, ambient, and solar sources. A preliminary optimization for different operating modes is conducted, paving the way for a holistic understanding of the intricate interplay between industry-specific thermal requirements and the vast spectrum of energy resources. This multidimensional approach contributes to the broader objective of advancing sustainable and efficient heat solutions within the framework of the SUSHEAT project.

1 INTRODUCTION

Rising energy costs, relying on fossil fuels due to the global crisis, and growing energy demands to reduce product carbon footprints are motivating companies in the world to devise strategies aimed at decarbonizing process heat (Schlosser *et al.*, 2023). Approximately 80% of the recent emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG) are corresponded to the demand for energy, particularly in the form of electricity and heat. This issue is of increasing importance for fossil energy in the industrial sector, which constituted approximately half of global GHG emissions in 2017 (EEA, 2020). An increase in energy consumption directly correlates with higher emissions, illustrating the close relationship between energy consumption and emissions (Mohamed and Lee, 2006). Final energy consumption (FEC) includes all the energy provided to different industrial sectors and serves as a measure of consumption at the ultimate energy consumption point (Eurostat, 2020). Figure 1 also illustrates an

examination of final energy consumption by end-use in EU28 in the year 2021, showing three main categories: transport (29.2%), households (27.9%), and industry sector (25.6%) (see Figure 1). It should be noted that international aviation and marine bunkers are not included in the transport category (European Commission, 2021).

Figure 1: Breakdown of final energy consumption by sector within the EU28 for the year 2021, represented as a percentage of the overall energy consumption, based on Terajoules (European Commission, 2021)

The decarbonization alternatives leading the industrial transition include improving process efficiency and implementing novel processes to reduce end-use energy consumption, using waste heat, and switching from fossil fuels to renewable sources of energy and raw materials (Marina *et al.*, 2021). Conventionally, industrial processes and operations requiring high-temperature heating (HTH) ranging between 100 and 125°C have been provided by low-pressure steam boilers, commonly fueled by fossil fuel energies or electrical heating systems that are not environmentally friendly (Bamigbetan *et al.*, 2019). Nevertheless, many industrial processes produce excess waste heat as a by-product, which is either free or requires the operation of cooling towers to dissipate it into the environment. This waste heat can be found in low temperatures and cannot be effectively reused in other processes in the industries. In the recent European energy framework, utilizing recovered industrial waste heat (IWH) supplies a suitable opportunity to replace primary energy consumption with a cost-effective, low-emission energy source (Miró *et al.*, 2016). However, concerning industrial waste heat, this potential is not only extensively unexplored but also unacknowledged. To promote the widespread adoption of recovered IWH, comprehensive assessments with extensive scope and detailed spatial resolution are essential. The optimal approach involves reusing this waste heat within the originating process, thereby avoiding scenarios where past investment decisions hinder additional energy efficiency enhancements. Furthermore, when high-temperature heat demand coincides with the availability of nearby low-temperature waste heat, it presents an opportunity to utilize heat pumps. These devices are among the technologies that exist for the recovery of industrial waste heat, enabling energy integration and enhancing overall system efficiency (Bamigbetan *et al.*, 2019). Accordingly, with the rising share of electricity being generated from renewable sources, the use of an electric-powered industrial heat pump is a robust option for a more sustainable industrial sector. Technologically, heat pump prototypes currently under development can achieve temperatures of up to 200°C and beyond (Schlosser *et al.*, 2023). Overall, the Stirling cycle HTWP operates based on the Stirling cycle, which involves compression and expansion of a working fluid. This cycle utilizes pistons or displacers to achieve compression and expansion, resulting in heat transfer at high temperatures. The efficiency of a Stirling cycle HTWP is typically lower than that of a Carnot cycle due to irreversibilities inherent in the mechanical components. On the other hand, the Carnot HTWP operates based on the Carnot cycle, which is a theoretical thermodynamic cycle representing the maximum efficiency achievable for a heat engine or heat pump operating between two temperature reservoirs. The Carnot cycle is characterized by isothermal compression and expansion processes, resulting in higher theoretical efficiency compared to other cycles (Tchanche *et al.*, 2010). In a Stirling cycle, the compression and expansion processes

occur at different temperatures, allowing for better utilization of heat sources and sinks with large temperature differentials. This feature makes Stirling cycle heat engines or heat pumps particularly suitable for low-temperature heat recovery applications, where the Carnot cycle's efficiency would be limited due to its theoretical maximum efficiency being dependent on the temperature difference between the hot and cold reservoirs (Tchanche et al., 2010). Additionally, Stirling cycle systems can be designed with simpler mechanical configurations compared to Carnot cycle systems, which often require complex components such as turbines or compressors. This simplicity can result in lower manufacturing and maintenance costs (Tchanche et al., 2010).

High-temperature heat pumps (HTHPs) with sink temperatures between 160°C and 200°C are being also developed by several research works (ISPT, 2020; DryEfficiency project, 2020), although their market implementation is expected to take several years. Enerin offers HTHPs utilizing helium (R704) as the working fluid and employing double-acting piston compressors within a Stirling cycle (Arpagaus et al., 2023). This configuration enables adaptable operating conditions, high lifting capabilities, and the delivery of temperatures exceeding 200°C (Arpagaus et al., 2023). Furthermore, Olvondo Technology's HighLift HTHP system, implemented in the heat pumps at AstraZeneca, Sweden, was designed to operate within this temperature range (Khan et al., 2021). Wolf and Bles (2016) assessed the potential application of heat pumps by considering 15% of Europe's overall industrial energy consumption.

Nonetheless, the lack of progress in developing products for higher temperatures is often due to inadequate comprehension by manufacturers of heat pumps for applications of industrial processes, and market demand. To address these constraints, the European Union (EU) funded the SUSHEAT project, whose main objective is to design a hybrid renewable heat upgrade system that aims to replace fossil fuels-based boilers in the European industrial landscape through three novel technologies: an advanced Stirling cycle-based HTHP capable of temperatures up to 250 °C, Phase Change Materials (PCM) bio-inspired TES system and Control and Integration Twin system. Accordingly, this paper presents the preliminary results of Work Package 2 (WP2) of the SUSHEAT project which assesses a qualitative potential application of the concept of this project to contribute to the decarbonization of the heat demand of the European industry.

This study explores the potential application of the European SUSHEAT project in meeting industrial heat demand. Section 2 introduces the SUSHEAT concept. Section 3 outlines energy consumption, heat demand, and industrial processes in the EU. Section 4 focuses on waste heat in industries and heat pumps. Section 5 summarizes the heat demand and waste heat temperature range in the case studies. Lastly, Section 6 presents the conclusions of this study.

2. THE SUSHEAT CONCEPT

Figure 2 shows the four main components that integrate the SUSHEAT system:

- a) High-temperature heat pump: Low-temperature heat sources (waste heat, cooling water, or ambient heat) will be upgraded via the Stirling-based-cycle heat pump to deliver high-temperature heat up to 250°C required for industrial processes, such as drying, distillation, or rapid heating on the SUSHEAT for the case studies. Utilizing both waste heat and electrical energy, a heat pump produces a steam temperature of up to 250°C and a pressure of 45 bar. This setup can realistically achieve a coefficient of performance for heating (COP_h) between 1.9 and 3.2.
- b) Thermal Energy Storage (TES): Technological improvements will be made for novel latent heat TES. Optimal Phase Change Material (PCM) will be studied and selected for the SUSHEAT hybrid renewable heat upgrade system. This system is designed to store surplus thermal energy harvested in peak solar periods and dispense it to processes as needed. Low-temperature TES typically ranges from 70-85°C, whereas high-temperature TES operates between 180-200°C.
- c) Linear Fresnel Collector (LFC) system: SUSHEAT uses off-the-shelf LFC that incorporates linear Fresnel mirrors for concentration, with an elevated receiver positioned at the apex so that the mirrors capture solar irradiance and focus it onto the receiver, where a heat transfer fluid (HTF) flows to absorb the heat for achieving a temperature up to 185°C. This heat is then

transferred to both the PCM storage system and various processes. SUSHEAT facilitates the extended integration of renewables to harvest energy from waste heat, ambient as a heat reservoir, and supporting industrial LFC operations within the temperature range of 150-250°C.

- d) Control and Integration Twin (CIT): The SUSHEAT CIT system will use a digital twin for experimental simulations and an AI-guided control system. This optimizes and improves energy management for processes in Industry 5.0.

Figure 2: The SUSHEAT system

3. ENERGY CONSUMPTION, HEAT DEMAND, AND INDUSTRIAL PROCESSES IN THE EU

3.1. Final energy consumption (FEC)

Figure 3 displays the FEC of the Sustainable Process Industry through Resource and Energy Efficiency (SPIRE) and non-SPIRE industries by the industrial sector at the EU27 level for the year 2021. The chemical and petrochemical industry emerged as the leading consumer, accounting for 2,159 PJ, or 21.5% of the overall FEC in the EU's industrial sector in 2021. It is closely followed by the non-metallic mineral industry with 1,420 PJ (14.1%) and the pulp, paper, and printing industry with 1,361 PJ (13.6%). Other sectors exceeding the 10% mark include food, beverages, and also tobacco (1,168 PJ or 11.6%) as well as iron and steel (1,027 PJ or 10.2%) (see Figure 3) (European Commission, 2021).

Figure 3: Final energy consumption (PJ) in the industry sectors within EU27 in 2021 (European Commission, 2021)

3.2. Heat demand

The contribution of the heat demand for each EU28 country in 2017 is shown in Figure 4 while a breakdown of the heat demand by the industrial sector is demonstrated in Figure 5. These figures are derived from the data cited in the references (Papapetrou *et al.*, 2018; European Commission, 2020). The total heat demand for the EU28 amounted to 1600 terawatt-hours (TWh). Figure 4 shows that a significant part of this demand came from Germany (22%), followed by France (10.4%), Italy (10.1%), the UK (8%), and Spain (7.8%), with the remaining countries contributing significantly lower percentages.

Figure 4: Heat demand breakdown by EU28 country (%) (Papapetrou *et al.*, 2018; European Commission, 2020)

Concerning the heat demand in each industrial sector, Figure 5 illustrates that the chemical and petrochemical sector recorded the highest demand at 328.8 TWh, followed by iron and steel (289.2 TWh), non-metallic minerals with a value of 279.4 TWh, and food and beverages with a value of 208.9 TWh). Subsequently, there were lower demands in paper, pulp, and print 106.3 TWh), machinery (95.4 TWh), non-ferrous metals (84.6 TWh), unspecified industries (82.8 TWh), and construction (63 TWh).

Figure 5: Breakdown of heat demand by industry in terawatt-hours (TWh) for the year 2017 (Tannous *et al.*, (2023))

The industrial sectors exhibiting the least heat demand were transport equipment (28.7 TWh), textile and leather (22.2 TWh), mining and quarrying with a value of 13.9 TWh, and wood products with a value of 3.7 TWh as shown in Figure 5 (Papapetrou *et al.*, 2018; European Commission, 2020). So, the industries with the greatest heat demand were identified in Germany, France, Italy, Spain, and the UK. Within EU28, SPIRE industries exhibited the highest overall heat demand.

3.3. Heat demand based on the temperature range for industrial sectors in the EU28

Figure 6 illustrates the heat demand per temperature range for the primary industrial sectors for the EU in 2017. This data was derived from the heat demand for the EU in 2017, and information on the breakdown of demand per temperature range provided by IRENA and Kosmadakis (2019). In the IRENA classification, heat demand is initially divided into three temperature ranges: (a) below 150°C, (b) 150-400 °C, and (c) above 400 °C. This involved using data from Kosmadakis (2019) for temperatures below 60 °C and between 60-150 °C. The analysis shows that iron and steel, and non-ferrous metals as well as non-metallic minerals have a relatively modest heat demand of 8% in the 60-400°C temperature range as depicted in Figure 6. In contrast, the chemical and petrochemical industry has a significant heat demand of 48% in the same temperature range, while the food and tobacco industry exceeds 90% (see Figure 6). Figure 6 demonstrates that in the 60-400°C temperature range, the shares of heat demand for mining and quarrying, transport equipment, machinery, textiles and leather, and other process heat are 92%, 89%, 89%, 77%, and 77%, respectively. According to reports, approximately 27% of the heat demand of processes in European nations falls within the range temperature between 100 and 200 °C (Profile of Heating and Cooling Demand, 2015). However, the majority of the demand for process heating is for higher temperatures.

Figure 6: The heat demand categorized by temperature range for industrial sectors in EU28 (ASTEP project, 2023)

3.4. Industrial processes and their required temperatures

Different industries and applications may require heat at different temperature levels to carry out their manufacturing or processing activities. Table 1 displays industrial processes requiring temperatures up to 250°C that could potentially benefit from implementing the SUSHEAT system. These industries typically operate at temperatures below 250°C, as indicated in Table 1 (Tannous *et al.*, 2023). The food industry is commonly categorized as operating at low temperatures, for activities like separation and

mixing, to as high as 250°C for baking and frying (Lauterbach *et al.*, 2012). Specifically, as shown in Table 1, in the canned food industry, the temperature requirements typically fall within the range of 110 to 120°C, primarily for sterilization processes (Lillo *et al.*, 2017). In the dairy industry, the highest temperature required for drying milk powder is between 160 and 205°C (see Table 1) (Ferry *et al.*, 2020). In the water industry, the highest temperature required is in the range of 130-150°C for wastewater evaporation (Lauterbach., *et al.*, 2012). The Iron and steel manufacturing process consists of several stages, each with its own temperature requirements. The temperature range for heating in this process is 180–220°C, while the non-ferrous metals industry for drying processes requires temperatures of 60 to 200°C (see Table 1) (ASTEP, 2023). Nevertheless, by integrating heat pump systems with solar energy, it is possible to meet the significant heat demand required for different processes. This hybrid system can be used for various processes such as drying, washing, cooking, sterilizing, and pasteurizing (Schmitt, 2018; Hasanuzzaman *et al.*, 2012; Kim *et al.*, 2023).

Table 1: Potential industrial processes suitable for implementing the SUSHEAT System

Industry	Processes	Required temperature (°C)	References
Food and Beverages	Frying and baking	Up to 250	(Lauterbach <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
Canned food	Sterilization	110-120	(Lillo <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Dairy	Drying	120-180	(Ferry <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
	Pasteurizing and Sterilization	60-145	(Lauterbach <i>et al.</i> , (2012); Lillo <i>et al.</i> , (2017)
Paper	Bleach	130-150	(Lillo <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Water	Evaporating of wastewater	130-150	(Plaza <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
Chemistry	Soaps	200-260	(Plaza <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
	Synthetic rubber	150-200	
	Process heat	120-180	(Lillo <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Agricultural products	Drying	80-200	(Lillo <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Textile	Degreasing	160-180	
	Drying	100-130	
Plastics	Drying	180-200	(Lillo <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Wood products	Pulp preparation	120-170	(Lillo <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Iron and steel	Heating	180–220	(ASTEP, 2023)
Non-ferrous metals	Drying	60-200	(Plaza <i>et al.</i> , 2014)

Regardless, it is imperative to specify both the heat consumption fulfilled by heat pumps and the proportion of the heat consumption by industry sectors. The conclusive step of this examination involves aligning the recoverable waste heat with the operation of industrial heat pumps to meet a portion of the heat demand.

Figure 7 shows the overall heat consumption potential of heat pumps across all considered industries, highlighting the most favorable sectors. In addition, at the top of each bar in the bands of temperature, the percentage of heat consumption that the upgraded heat can address is shown. Within the temperature range between 100°C and 200°C, industrial heat pumps exhibit the capability to cover a portion of favorable heat consumption across various sectors, excluding industries of iron and steel, which lack any waste heat within this range and thus have zero potential. In industries of non-ferrous metal, the potential of heat production of heat pumps surpasses heat consumption by 11% (with 4.39 TWh/year of available heat upgraded in comparison to 3.89 TWh/year of heat consumption), enabling the coverage of 100% of heat consumption in the given temperature range (Figure 7).

Figure 7: The heat consumption addressed by industrial heat pumps within per EU country across all considered industries at 100–200 °C temperature range (Kosmadakis, 2019)

This percentage decreases to around 35% in the non-metallic minerals and drops to nearly 11% in paper industries (Figure 7). For the food sector, the proportion is roughly 6.5%, and in chemical industries, it is even lower (Kosmadakis, 2019). In industries with lower energy demands, the potential for sustainable solutions is notably limited, accounting for only 1-2% of heat consumption. Nevertheless, viable sustainable approaches can still be achieved, even within these sectors, as seen in the textile industry (Pulat et al., 2009).

4. WASTE HEAT IN THE INDUSTRIES AND HEAT PUMPS

4.1. Waste heat per industry in the EU28

A survey of the energy consumption in the industrial sectors of the EU28 is done, accompanied by a first evaluation of the potential for waste heat. Table 2, based on information from reference (Panayiotou *et al.*, 2017), illustrates the shares of waste heat potential for individual industries. Table 2 indicates that the Iron and Steel sector accounts for the largest portion of waste heat at 11.40%, whereas the Food and Tobacco industry contributes 8.64% of the total waste heat. The distribution of energy consumption among 13 industrial industries in 2016 was computed at 3217.85 TWh, with a predicted potential for waste heat with a value of 336.9 TWh (European Commission, 2018).

Table 2: The percentage of waste heat potential per industry of the EU28 (Panayiotou *et al.*, 2017)

Type of industry	Waste heat potential (%)
Iron and Steel	11.40
Chemical and Petrochemical	11.00
Non-ferrous metal industry	9.59
Non-metallic minerals	11.40
Food and Tobacco	8.64
Paper Pulp and Print	10.56
Wood and Wood Products	6.00
Textile and Leather	11.04
Other	10.38

4.2. Characterizing process heat demand, and waste heat for heat pumps

Table 3 shows the calculated amounts of process and waste heat for the four sectors within the temperature range below 200°C in EU28. In addition, the amounts of process and also waste heat within

the temperature range below 150°C are highlighted. The amount of waste heat is particularly noticeable in the refining sector, where the magnitude of waste heat significantly surpasses that of process heat. This characteristic is inherent to the sector, which is characterized by a significant demand for process heat at given temperatures above 200°C, that is subsequently removed from the process at temperatures below 200°C. Conversely, for other industries like paper and food, where almost all process heat is below 200°C, the overall balance remains incomplete, resulting in a lack of comparability between process and waste heat values. The assessment of the processes identified a total of 1123 PJ/y of process heat and 1130 PJ/y of waste heat. Also, the greatest amounts of process heat were found in the paper and chemical sectors with 356 PJ/y and 355 PJ/y, respectively (Marina *et al.*, 2021) (see Table 3). The food sector and the refinery sector also showed significant amounts, although lower, with 193 PJ/y and 219 PJ/y respectively. For waste heat, the refinery sector stood out with the highest calculated value of 465 PJ/y, followed by the chemical sector with 337 PJ/y, mainly due to the use of condensers in the processes of distillation. Significant sources of waste heat were found in the paper industries (231 PJ/y) and the food sector (97 PJ/y) (Marina *et al.*, 2021) (see Table 3). Using high-temperature heat pump technology, the SUSHEAT project has the capability to convert a significant amount of excess waste heat into heat suitable for industrial operations, with an estimated yield of 47 terawatt-hours (Profile of Heating and Cooling Demand in 2015).

Table 3: An overview of the cumulative process and waste heat (less than 150°C and 200°C) within the EU28 processes across the heat pump analysis (Marina *et al.*, 2021)

Sector	<150°C		<200°C	
	Process Heat (PJ/y)	Waste Heat (PJ/y)	Process Heat (PJ/y)	Waste Heat (PJ/y)
Paper	228	231	356	231
Chemical	295	320	355	337
Food	130	96	193	97
Refinery	92	393	219	465
Total (Σ)	745	1039	1123	1130

5. HEAT DEMAND AND WASTE HEAT TEMPERATURE RANGE IN THE CASE STUDIES

To validate the effectiveness of the SUSHEAT concept, two main case studies have been selected: the dairy industry Mandrekas, located in Greece, and the fishmeal company Pelagia, located in Norway. Thermal demand profiles for two primary use cases, Mandrekas and Pelagia, detail heating needs, design specifications, and operational constraints are indicated in this study. Table 4 shows the specifications of two case studies used in this research work. Mandrekas serves as a case study to validate the effectiveness of the SUSHEAT system, which includes integration of solar energy to raise the heat level to 190°C. The production process in Mandrekas requires steam generation at 8 bar (175 °C) for milk pasteurization. 70 % of the steam produced is used for pasteurization (operating at a pressure of 3 bar), 25% for yoghurt ripening, and 5% for cleaning in place (CIP). The condensate is returned to the steam condensate tank as a saturated liquid at 1 bar and 100 °C. Mandrekas has calculated losses in steam generation and distribution to be 25%. However, there is potential for the use of SUSHEAT concept in dairy processes to meet heating requirements of the boiler (175 °C) as well as homogenization (67 °C), pressurization (80 °C), and mixing (28-30 °C). The manufacturing facilities at Pelagia utilize steam boilers fired by fossil fuels to generate steam at 175°C. This steam is utilized to heat cookers and dryers for general processing and to provide heat for the final stages of product drying, typically ranging from 200 to 250°C. The SUSHEAT technology solutions need to be capable of receiving waste heat in the temperature range of 60 to 90°C and transferring it to a range of 150 to 250°C. In the year 2022, Pelagia company recorded a total thermal energy consumption of 46,487,520 kWh and electricity consumption of 7,583,053 kWh. The data shows a significant increase in energy consumption of Mandrekas over the last five years, from 752,019 kWh in 2015 to 1,582,629 kWh in 2019. Concerning waste heat, it is important to highlight that in Mandrekas, the waste streams from

homogenization and pasteurization processes are at temperatures between 67 °C and 80 °C, respectively. Meanwhile, in Pelagia, the temperature of waste streams from dirty steam evaporation ranges between 95-98 °C, dirty condensate is at 75 °C, and humid air from the hot air drier reaches 70 °C.

Table 4: The specification details of case studies

Company	Country	Steam temperature of boiler (°C)	Waste heat temperature (°C)	Total energy consumption (kWh)
Mandrekas	Greece	175	67-80	LPG: 1,582,629
Pelagia	Norway	175	70-98	Thermal: 46,487,520 Electricity: 7,583,053

It is worth mentioning that the heat pump used in the SUSHEAT concept achieves a coefficient of performance (COP) of 2.8 with a temperature ratio of 1.26, operating within a temperature range of 165°C to 250°C. Additionally, for temperatures ranging from 70°C to 250°C, the COP is measured at 1.9 with a ratio of 1.52 for Mandrekas and Pelagia systems.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents the initial results of WP2 in the SUSHEAT project, which includes a High Temperature-Heat Pump (HTHP), PCM bio-inspired TES system, and Control and Integration Twin (CIT) system. It assesses the potential of the project to lower carbon emissions in the heat demand of European industry. The classification of heat demand into temperature low, low-medium, medium, and high-temperature ranges served as the basis for assessing the technical potential of HTHP systems to provide low-carbon heating for industrial processes. This study provides thermal demand profiles for two main use cases namely Mandrekas and Pelagia industries, outlining their heating requirements, design specifications, and operating limits. The innovative SUSHEAT concept designs are introduced, providing adaptable solutions to address the heat requirements of the European industry. The results showed that the total heat demand for the EU28 amounted to 1600 TWh. The allocation of energy consumption across 13 industrial sectors in 2016 amounted to 3217.85 TWh, with an estimated potential for waste heat reaching 336.9 TWh. For these specified industrial sectors, the industrial heat demand has been quantified in the temperature range between 150°C and 250°C, which is achievable by the SUSHEAT system. Moreover, with the aid of high-temperature heat pump technology, the SUSHEAT project can transform a considerable portion of the surplus waste heat potential into heat for industrial processes, estimated at 47 TWh. The comprehensive information presented here invites a thorough exploration of SUSHEAT's potential to contribute significantly to the decarbonization of heat demand in the European industrial landscape.

NOMENCLATURE

Acronyms

EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
FEC	Final energy consumption
CIT	Control and Integration Twin
IWH	Industrial waste heat
HTHP	High-Temperature Heat Pump
COPh	Coefficient of performance
PCM	Phase Change Material
HTF	Heat transfer fluid
SPIRE	Sustainable Process Industries through Resource & Energy Efficiency
LFR	Linear Fresnel Reflector

SUSHEAT	Smart Integration of Waste and Renewable Energy for Sustainable Heat Upgrade in the Industry
SC-HP	Stirling-cycle-based heat pump
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
LFC	Linear Fresnel Collector
PJ	PetaJoules
CIP	Cleaning in place
CIT	Control and Integration Twin
ΔT	Minimum temperature difference ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)

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